

WASTE4think seeks to move forward the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto, demonstrating the value of integrating and validating a set of 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover all the waste value chain.

- C** The coastal municipality of **CASCAIS** (PT)
- Z** The industrialized town of **ZAMUDIO** (ES)
- S** The residential town of **SEVESO** (IT)
- H** The business city of **HALANDRI** (GR)

COORDINATOR

DeustoTech

WASTE
4think

CASCAIS

WASTE4think.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995.

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Description

The coastal town of Cascais (Portugal) is a renowned tourism destination. Hence, environmental values are of crucial relevance to the municipality. However, this is a demanding task as Cascais has over 206.000 inhabitants and over 1,2 million tourists per year.

Objectives

The Waste4think project in Cascais is a test to the implementation of new technologies to help decision makers within the smart city scope of action. This also includes a valuable approach based on citizen participation to learn from their behaviours in order to develop a new waste management system.

Eco-Solutions

- The main objective is the implementation of PAYT (Pay-as-you-Throw) as a solution to increase consumer's environmental behaviour and awareness.

- The implementation of this system will be gradual with a close interaction between the service and the users since it is going to suppose a change of recycling habits: use of an access card to open a lock mechanism and a new invoice system.

- To achieve this, a communication campaign will be developed carrying out several activities with local population, tourists and local schools by an environmental awareness dedicated team:

1. Training and workshop sessions

2. APPs to engage the community in the PAYT implementation

3. Management of events

4. Gamification

5. Mobilization of people in social network groups

Expected results

- 8% reduction of waste generation
- 20% increase in waste sorting
- 10% saving of management costs
- 10% reduction of GHG emissions